

March 2016

VirusCollect: Fulfilling the need for a common reference collection of plant viruses and viroids

Plant diseases, including many plant viruses, are a continuous threat to the cost-effective and safe production of food and cause significant losses in yield and quality of many important crops. It is therefore essential to minimise the impact of plant diseases through an effective and coordinated system of legislation, plant passports and testing laboratories. In such system, reliable and cost-effective diagnosis methods for plant viruses are essential. These only can be developed, validated and implemented when suitable reference materials are available. Historically, reference materials were supplied from collections maintained by European universities and research institutions. However the maintenance of such collections had come under severe pressure due to a decrease in the number of scientists (virologists in particular) and allocated budgets. For plant viruses and viroids, type isolates (if still available) were dispersed between different public and/or private collections (Roehorst *et al.*, 2013).

The Euphresco project VirusCollect aimed to establish a common reference collection of viruses and viroids by linking collections of individual institutions via Q-bank.

To establish international collaboration on virus collections between National Plant Protection Organisations and allied institutions, basic requirements had to be fulfilled. Standard operating procedures (SOP's) were developed and implemented in participating laboratories to guarantee the quality of isolates and data, i.e. on characterization and inclusion, maintenance, release and production of reference materials.

The Q-bank Viruses and Viroids database <http://www.q-bank.eu/Virus/> provides information on the nature of viruses and viroids.

To ensure better accessibility to the public, the design and contents of the database were improved. Over 1000 virus species were included and relevant information for each species is now provided.

EU-regulated/ recommended for regulation species were marked as such and linked to the EPPO Global Database whenever possible.

